

***In Silico* Drug Design, Synthesis And *In Vitro* Evaluation of Certain Piperine Derivatives as Anti Alzheimer's Agents**

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurological illness that gradually impairs thinking and memory abilities, leading to the ultimate inability to perform even the most basic tasks. Black pepper contains an alkaloid called piperine, which has antidepressant, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and neuroprotective properties. The primary goal of the current work was to use structural alteration of piperine to develop and create new active derivatives of piperine that exhibit anti-Alzheimer's action by inhibiting the cholinesterase enzymes (AChE & BuChE).

In the present study, about 26 semisynthetic piperine derivatives were subjected to ADMET properties, molecular docking studies using AutoDock 4.2 against target enzymes AChE (4ey7) and BuChE (4BDS). From in silico study, the compounds were selected based on BBB barrier penetration and docking scores. A total of 3 compounds (PIP -4, PIP - 5 and PIP - 26) were selected and synthesized by three schemes with various substitutions. Analytical studies (UV & IR) were done to confirm its structure, and in vitro cholinesterase inhibitory activity was performed. The selected piperine derivatives were examined for acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase inhibitory activity. The absorbance of all the piperine derivatives was decreased upon increasing the concentration of drugs in a dose-dependent manner. The order of potency was based on IC₅₀ values. All the determinations were carried out in triplicate, and the values are expressed as the mean ± SEM. Hence, PIP-5 possessed good AChE inhibitory activity (56±0.45 µg/ml), and also PIP-5 exhibited excellent BuChE inhibitory activity (30±0.32 µg/ml) when compared to other selected piperine derivatives and the standard drug rivastigmine. Thus, the compound (PIP-5) may offer a promising and new therapeutic lead for the treatment of AD, which needs further research.

Keywords: In Silico, Drug design, Piperine, Docking studies, Alzheimer's disease, Auto Dock 4.2.

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a brain disease that gradually impairs thinking and memory abilities, leading to the eventual inability to perform even the most basic tasks. The late-onset symptoms of the disease typically start to show up in the middle of a

person's 60s. It is quite uncommon for someone to get early-onset Alzheimer's between the ages of thirty and sixty. The most prevalent cause of dementia in older persons is Alzheimer's disease^[1]. Approximately 70% of dementia is thought to be caused by it. According to the Alzheimer's Association, 81% of AD patients are 75 years of age or older, making aging the biggest

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

risk factor for the disease's development. The illness bears Dr. Alois Alzheimer's name. The illness bears Dr. Alois Alzheimer's name. Dr. Alzheimer discovered alterations in a woman's brain tissue in 1906 after she passed away from an uncommon mental disease. Her symptoms included erratic behavior, language issues, and memory loss. When he studied her brain after she passed away, he discovered several aberrant clusters (now known as amyloid plaques) and twisted fiber bundles (now known as tau or neurofibrillary tangles). These brain tangles and plaques are still regarded as some of the primary characteristics of Alzheimer's disease. The lack of connections between the brain's neurons is another characteristic. Neurons carry messages from the brain to the body's muscles and organs as well as between various areas of the brain.[1,2] The damaged brain is characterized by the widespread distribution of two types of aberrant structures: so-called senile plaques and neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs). It also shows signs of astrogliosis, nerve cell shrinkage, and neuronal death. In the 1980s, immunochemical and biochemical analyses demonstrated that NFT comprises bundles of paired helical filaments of the microtubule-associated protein tau, whereas senile plaque is made up of amyloid fibrils made of the amyloid β ($A\beta$) peptide. Amyloid β precursor protein (APP) is sequentially cleaved by β -secretase (BACE 1) and γ -secretase (a complex containing presenilin 1) to produce $A\beta$, a peptide with roughly 40 amino acids.^[3]

STAGES IN ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

Alzheimer's disease usually starts out slowly and gets worse over time. Most parts of your brain eventually become affected by Alzheimer's disease. The illness may impact thinking, movement, personality, problem-solving, language, memory, and judgment. Alzheimer's disease is characterized by five stages

- Mild cognitive impairment due to Alzheimer's disease
- Mild dementia due to Alzheimer's disease
- Moderate dementia due to Alzheimer's disease

- Severe dementia due to Alzheimer's disease.

Preclinical Alzheimer's disease

Alzheimer's disease begins long before any symptoms become apparent. This stage is called preclinical Alzheimer's disease, and it's usually identified only in research settings. This stage of Alzheimer's can last for years, possibly even decades.

Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) due to Alzheimer's disease

Memory and thinking skills are slightly altered in those with mild cognitive impairment. When it comes to material that is often easy to recall, including recent events, appointments, or conversations, people with MCI may experience memory problems. Individuals with MCI may also struggle to accurately estimate the number of steps or sequence required to do a task, or they may struggle to estimate how long a task would take.

Mild dementia due to Alzheimer's disease

When it is evident to family members and medical professionals that a patient is experiencing severe memory and cognitive impairment that affects day-to-day functioning, Alzheimer's disease is frequently identified in the moderate dementia stage. Memory loss of recent events, trouble handling complicated problems and making accurate judgments, personality changes, trouble organizing and articulating thoughts, and getting lost or misplacing possessions are all possible symptoms of mild dementia.

Moderate dementia due to Alzheimer's disease

People with Alzheimer's disease who are in the mild dementia stage become increasingly disoriented and forgetful and require more assistance with everyday tasks and personal hygiene. Alzheimer's patients in the moderate dementia stage may: Need assistance with certain everyday tasks; exhibit worsening confusion and deteriorating judgment; and experience even more memory loss, experience notable behavioural and personality changes.

Severe Alzheimer's disease- related dementia

In the advanced stages of the illness, known as severe dementia due to Alzheimer's disease, movement and physical abilities are increasingly affected, and brain function continues to deteriorate. People typically endure a deterioration in their physical abilities, daily assistance with personal care, and the loss of coherent communication in the later stages of severe dementia caused by Alzheimer's disease..^[4]

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

Alzheimer's disease targets neurotransmitters, brain cells, and nerves. Protein clumps grow around the brain's cells as a result of the breakdown of these components. These clusters are referred to as plaques, and when bundles begin to break down additional connections between brain cells, the disease deteriorates. Because of the etiological variables, the cerebral cortex's nerve cells' proteins change, neurofibrillary tangles and plaques accumulate, granulo-vascular degeneration occurs, cholinergic nerve cells are lost, and memory, function, and cognition are lost ^[5]

ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE SYMPTOMS

Memory loss: A person may struggle to retain information and assimilate new information.
Cognitive deficits: A person may struggle with judgment, logic, and complicated tasks.
Recognition issues: A person may lose their ability to utilize simple tools or to identify faces or objects. Eye difficulties are not the cause of these problems.

Spatial awareness issues include trouble balancing, tripping, or spilling more frequently, as well as trouble orienting garments to the body when putting on clothes.

Speaking, reading, or writing issues: A person may experience trouble coming up with common words or they may make more mistakes in their writing, speech, or spelling.

Behavior or personality changes: A person may exhibit compulsive, obsessive, or socially

inappropriate behavior; a decrease in empathy; a loss of interest in or motivation for activities they typically enjoy; or an increase in the frequency of being upset, angry, or worried..^[6]

CHOLINESTERASE ENZYMES' ROLE IN AD

Cholinesterase (ChE) enzymes facilitate the hydrolysis of synaptic acetylcholine (ACh), which is essential for controlling cholinergic neurotransmission. There are two forms of ChE that are widely distributed throughout the body and have different roles depending on where they are located, which are still unknown. Butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) is typically associated with and secreted from glial cells in the central nervous system, whereas acetylcholinesterase (AChE) is primarily found in neurons. About 90% of the ChE activity in the typical human brain's temporal cortex is attributed to AChE, with the remaining 10% coming from BuChE. ACh can be bound and cleaved by both enzymes, but until recently, little was known about BuChE's relative role in controlling ACh levels. ACh can be bound and cleaved by both enzymes, but until recently, little was known about BuChE's relative role in controlling ACh levels. There is mounting evidence that both AChE and BuChE may play a significant role in the onset and progression of Alzheimer's disease (AD), in addition to their roles in normal cholinergic function. In contrast, levels of BuChE activity can rise by up to 90% as AD progresses, whereas up to 45% of AChE may be lost in specific brain regions..^[7]

ACETYLCHOLINESTERASE (AChE)

Reduced levels of the neurotransmitter acetylcholine (ACh), choline acetylcholinesterase (the enzyme that limits the rate at which ACh is synthesized), and the ACh-hydrolyzing enzyme acetylcholinesterase (AChE) are linked to the consequent decrease in cholinergic activity, which is correlated with the severity of cognitive impairment. The synaptic hydrolysis of ACh, which stops its neurotransmitter action, and the coregulation of ACh levels appear to be simultaneous activities of AChE and BuChE. Despite belonging to the same pharmacological class as cholinesterase, they differ structurally. While tacrine and rivastigmine co-inhibit both AChE and BuChE, donepezil and galantamine exhibit relative preference for AChE. Cholinergic hypofunction may

arise from β -Amyloid (A β) peptide's physiological modulation of cholinergic function, and soluble A β concentrations too low to cause neurotoxicity can prevent the synthesis and release of ACh. The hippocampus and cortex seem to be the only parts of the brain affected by these effects.^[7]

BUTYRYLCHOLINESTERASE (BuChE)

In the AD brain, BuChE activity may be elevated by 40% to 90% overall. The temporal cortex and hippocampus, which are the brain regions most impacted by AD, are where BuChE activity increases most frequently. Among ChE-positive neurons in the human amygdala, BuChE activity is more prevalent than AChE activity. Within the same neuronal elements in the human hippocampus, AChE and BuChE have been discovered to coexist. The neuritic plaques of AD contain high amounts of BuChE. The toxicity of P-amyloid peptide is increased in vitro by both AChE and BuChE. It appears that both AChE and BuChE play a role in the conversion of diffuse P-amyloid into compact neuritic plaques. The ApoE4 gene and the K-variant BuChE may be the cause of late-onset AD. When an AChE-specific inhibitor is present, the human brain's ACh surrogate acetylthiocholine is hydrolyzed by BuChE. When mutant mice lack AChE activity, BuChE hydrolyzes ACh. Rats treated with BuChE-specific inhibitors have higher amounts of extracellular ACh. Rats with BuChE-specific inhibitors have better cognitive function. In the CSF of AD patients, dual inhibition causes a dose-dependent decrease in AChE and BuChE activity. Clinical advantages are associated with inhibition of AChE and BuChE.^[5]

INTRODUCTION TO DRUG DISCOVERY

The process of finding chemicals that may one day be used as medicinal agents is known as drug discovery. Finding new molecular entities that could be useful in treating illnesses that meet the criteria for presenting unmet medical needs is a major objective of drug discovery campaigns. Basic research, feasibility studies, discovery programs, non-clinical development, as well as clinical development, are some of the stages involved in drug discovery. Drug design concepts are necessary because they can be used to increase ADME qualities, selectivity of action, prevent adverse effects from current drugs,

create drugs with more potency, specificity, and lower toxicity, and create drugs that will compete with those already on the market.

DISEASE SELECTION:

An aberrant condition that adversely affects the structure or function of all or a portion of an organism is called a disease. Focusing on diseases where new medications are needed is crucial. To find effective treatment candidates, the disease must be studied at the molecular and genetic levels.

TARGET SELECTION AND VALIDATION:

Prior to design, a thorough analysis of biological targets, such as enzymes, receptors, etc., that are necessary for the existence of microbial species or that are in charge of the manifestation of disease, should be conducted. This can be accomplished by breaking down complicated illnesses into their most basic elements. The goal of target identification is to comprehend the biological mechanism behind illness. Target validation is the process of examining the target's characteristics using the genome's sources.^[8]

LEAD IDENTIFICATION:

The chemicals derived from a database of hits are known as leads. Candidates with chemical entities in crude form that have been found to have specific pharmacological activity are known as hits. Standard databases or specially created libraries can be used to retrieve hits. One of the most important phases in the drug design process is hits to lead conversion. To increase its efficacy, pharmacodynamic profile, and pharmacokinetic profile, the selected lead should be studied and optimized with fragments. This will help anticipate candidates with the fewest toxicities and side effects. Conversion from hit to lead is possible.

Subset selection and similarity search:

Finding complimentary molecules in a vast chemical space is a significant challenge in drug design. There are roughly 106 chemicals in databases, and the estimated number of tiny drug-like molecules is around 10200. There are roughly 103 of these commercial medications. Thus, there is a mere 0.1% chance of choosing the lead chemical. Therefore,

fingerprints, 2D or topological descriptors, and 3D or geometrical descriptors are used in the targeted library selection process.

Synthesis of combinatorial libraries:

Combinatorial libraries are collections of many synthetic, chemical, or biological molecules that are created and kept in mixtures that take into account every potential pairing of the building blocks. Millions of molecular structures can be created with this lab approach, and their biological activity can be examined. There are more molecules available for combinatorial synthesis than there are compounds that can be created. Selecting a subset of fragments is necessary to lower the number of compounds.

Virtual screening:

One of the most popular strategies for hit-to-lead conversion is virtual screening. In drug development, it is a computer method that searches libraries of small compounds to find the structures that have the highest probability of binding to a therapeutic target, usually an enzyme or protein receptor. It is possible to conduct virtual screening.

Ligand-based virtual screening:

When the target structure is unknown, ligand-based virtual screening is used. Chemical structure databases are searched for compounds that share a pharmacophore or substructure with a known active (pharmacophore substructure searching) or that are comparable to known actives (similarity searching). Ligand-based virtual screening includes machine learning techniques, pharmacophore-based screening, and similarity searches.

Structure-based virtual screening:

When the goal structure is known, it is carried out. The target molecule's possible ligand binding sites (active sites) are found utilizing tools such as Ligand Plot, on site Finder, and other resources. The chosen target binding site is docked with the chemicals from the database.

LEAD OPTIMIZATION:

The pharmacokinetic profile of the discovered leads needs to be assessed. Lipinski's rule of five, which specifies that a chemical for improved oral bioavailability should have, is the basis for the first filtering.

- Molecular weight less than 500g/mol.
- Lipophilicity or logP less than 5.
- Hydrogen bond donors less than 10.
- Hydrogen bond acceptors less than 5.
- No of rotational bonds less than 5.

Numerous additional pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic elements are examined, such as blood-brain barrier, binding to human serum albumin, hepatotoxic symptoms, teratogenicity, mutagenicity, and human intestine absorption. Several commercial and scholarly software programs are used to perform in silico optimization techniques.

DOCKING STUDIES:

Docking is the process by which the proper ligands in three-dimensional structures engage with the binding pockets of an enzyme's three-dimensional structure. As a result of docking investigations, the energy commonly referred to as binding energy will be found along the conformational posture^[10]. Docking can be accomplished via

Ligand-based docking:

When the three-dimensional geometry of the targets is unclear, ligand-based docking is used. Understanding additional compounds that bind to the biological target of interest is essential for ligand-based drug design, also known as indirect drug design. The target structure can be built using the ligand pharmacophore knowledge.

Structure-based docking:

Structure-based drug design, also known as direct drug design, is predicated on an understanding of the biological target's three-dimensional structure as determined by techniques like NMR spectroscopy or X-ray crystallography. With the help of interactive

visuals and a medicinal chemist's intuition, candidate medications that are anticipated to bind to the biological target with high affinity and selectivity can be created based on the target's structure. One technique that can be applied to structure-based docking is de novo drug design. Both the linking approach and the construction method can be used to accomplish this. The construction process involves embedding a single small fragment and gradually constructing small fragments to build up the ligand molecules within the binding pocket's restrictions. The linking procedure involves inserting tiny molecules into the binding pocket that are retrieved from databases. Small pieces are gradually joined to create a new molecule that is the target's size and form complement.

Drug receptor interactions:

The relationship between a drug and its receptor is known as pharmacodynamics. Pharmacophores are the groups on a molecule that bind with a receptor and are known to be responsible for the activity. The auxophore, the primary atom in the molecule, is necessary to preserve the molecule's integrity and keep the pharmacophoric groups in their proper locations. It is necessary to remove certain auxophores from the lead chemical because they may prevent the pharmacophore from binding. It's possible that some of the auxophore's atoms are floating around inside the receptor, not attaching to it or blocking the pharmacophoric atoms from binding. It is best to alter these atoms without compromising their efficacy. Covalent bonds, ionic contacts, hydrogen bonds, charge transfer complexes, ion-dipole and dipole-dipole interactions, hydrophobic interactions, and van der Waals' interactions are some of the forces at play.

Scoring Functions:

A scoring function is a precise calculation of the relative binding energies and affinities of the protein and the ligand, or binding poses. Force-field-based, empirical, and knowledge-based scoring functions can all be used to get it.

PROTOCOLS FOR SOFTWARE

Databases, servers, and software are all related to computer-aided drug design techniques. SMILES notation is generated and structures are constructed using the structure drawing software. The software utilized includes ChemDraw, ChemSketch, MarvinSketch, and others. Since the majority of software recognizes structures with the .pdb extension, the structure should be changed into a protein data bank extension after it has been built. Open Babel, Smiles Translator (<https://cactus.nci.nih.gov/translate/>), and other tools are typically utilized. Software such as iGEMDockv2 (<http://gemdock.life.nctu.edu.tw/download.php>) is used for virtual screening approaches. For example, Glide (<https://www.schrodinger.com/products/gleide>). Databases that offer vast chemical spaces, such as ZINC (<https://zinc.docking.org/>), CSD, etc., can be used for hit selection. Accelrys Accord for Excel (accelrys-accord-for-excel.software.informer.com), the Lipinski filter (www.molinspiration.com), and other tools can be used to anticipate pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic outcomes. Software such as Autodock4.2 (<https://autodock.scripps.edu/>), Schrodinger Maestro (<https://www.schrodinger.com/products/gleide>), and others can be used to carry out docking protocols and create binding poses and binding energies.^[8]

A DRUG CANDIDATE FOR ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE: PIPERINE

About 90% of black pepper is made up of piperine, the primary alkaloid. Piperidine, a heterocyclic molecule, is the source of the fiery flavor and pungency of black pepper, *Piper nigrum* (Piperaceae), and *Piper longum* L. Piperine, which makes up around 90% of black pepper, is the primary alkaloid found in medicinal plants. It comes from the heterocyclic molecule piperidine and gives black pepper, *Piper nigrum* (Piperaceae), and *Piper longum* L their fiery, pungency-producing flavor. For many years, people have utilized medicinal herbs as food, spices, and as a cure for a variety of illnesses in traditional medicine. One of the most popular spices in the world is *Piper nigrum*, which is a member of the Piperaceae family. The phytochemical piperine is responsible for its unique, sharp flavor. In addition to being used as a spice, *P. nigrum* is widely employed in medicine, preservation, and fragrance. Piperine, which is linked

to the pepper plant, ranges in quantity from 2.4% to 7.4% in black pepper. The nitrogen atom of piperine, a N-acylpiperidine, is replaced with a (1E,3E)-1-(1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)-5-oxopenta-1,3-dien-5-yl group. It is an alkaloid that was isolated from the *Piper nigrum* plant. It functions as a plant metabolite, a dietary ingredient, an NF-kappaB inhibitor, and a metabolite of human blood serum. It belongs to the region carboxamide, N-acylpiperidine, piperidine alkaloid, and benzodioxole groups. An (E, E)-piperic acid is the source of it.

STRUCTURE:

Figure 1: Structure of piperine

PROPERTIES:

Table 1: Properties of Piperine

Chemical formula	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ NO ₃
Molar mass	285.343g.mol ⁻¹
Density	1.193 g/cm ³
Melting point	130°C (266°F; 403 K)
Boiling point	Decomposes
Solubility in water	40mg/l
Solubility in ethanol	Soluble
Solubility in chloroform	1g/1.7ml

MEDICINAL USES:

In a variety of in vitro and in vivo experimental trials, piperine exhibits a wide range of pharmacological actions, including antiproliferative, anticancer, anti-angiogenesis, antioxidant, antidiabetic, anti-obesity, cardioprotective, antibacterial, antiaging, and immunomodulatory properties. Its anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, hepatoprotective, and neuroprotective qualities have also been reported. The medicinal and health-promoting properties of piperine are highlighted and discussed in this review, along with potential mechanisms of action for disease prevention and health promotion.^[9]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Software and databases used

Accelrys discovery studio viewer 4.0.1, RCSB protein data bank, MGL tools-AutoDock 4.2, Python 2.7 molecule viewer 1.5.6, Vision 1.5.6, Cygwin 64, ACD ChemSketch, Online SMILES translator, PreADMET, and Molinspiration were among the databases and software utilized for in silico docking experiments.

Raw materials and chemicals:

Sri Ramakrishna Hospital Pharmacy in Coimbatore provided the rivastigmine. We bought pure pepper from Namakkal's Kolli Hills. Toluene, ethyl acetate, cyclohexane, benzyl amine, sucrose, Tris-HCL buffer, sodium azide, glutathione, potassium phosphate buffer, ethanol, dichloromethane, diethyl ether, potassium hydroxide, 4-chloroaniline, p-fluoroaniline, O-toluidine, and bovine serum albumin were all of analytical grade and were purchased from local vendors in Coimbatore.

The following instruments were used: nuclear magnetic resonance spectrometer-NMR-300 MHz, centrifuge, Jasco V-630 UV spectrophotometer, Jasco FT/IR-4100, MR-VIS visual melting range device (LABINDIA), and mass spectroscopy.

IN SILICO STUDIES

Lead and target selection

The anti-Alzheimer's activity was the main focus of this study. Acetylcholine esterase and butyrylcholine esterase enzymes were chosen as the study's target

based on the literature evaluation and the most recent research on Alzheimer's disease. The RCSB protein data bank provided the PDB structures for AChE (PDB ID: 4ey7) and BuChE (PDB ID: 4BDS). For the investigation, piperine's semisynthetic derivatives were created and employed.

Assessment of the qualities of drug likeness

The drug-likeness score and calculations of steric, hydrophobic, electronic, and hydrogen bonding properties were used to characterize a total of 26 molecules from three piperine derivatives. Pharmaceutical and pharmacokinetic features, such as chemical stability, solubility, distribution profile, and bioavailability, can be optimized with the aid of the drug-likeness score theory. The molecular descriptors, such as Lipinski's Rule-of-Five (Ro5), have been designed as logically instructive and predictive. Using data on solubility, diffusion, Log P, molecular weight, and other factors, the improved oral absorption of the ligands and drug similarity ratings were created. Lipinski's rule of five was assessed using Molinspiration software.

Lipinski's Rule of 5 calculations

- Opened the Molinspiration home page (<http://www.molinspiration.com/>).
- For calculating Molinspiration, a JAVA program was loaded on the computer.
- Click the calculation of molecular properties of drug likeness.
- Draw the structure of flavonoids in the active window.
- Click calculate properties and predict bioactivity.
- Save the properties.

The compounds that passed the Lipinski rule of five were taken for further evaluation of ADMET properties.^[8]

Assessment of ADMET characteristics

The software PreADMET was used to conduct the ADMET studies for the chosen piperine variants. The

distribution and metabolism of the chosen ligands were assessed based on this absorption. Using ChemSketch software, the 2D structure was simply added to PreADMET to perform ADMET screening. Data for descriptors include hepatotoxicity, carcinogenicity, water solubility, plasma protein binding, blood brain barrier (BBB), and more. Several descriptors were tabulated following the structure's loading through the function model.^[11]

In silico docking study on AChE and BuChE using Autodock 4.2

The compounds were docked against the enzymes monoamine oxidase B and catechol-O-methyl transferase using AutoDock 4.2 software.

PIPERINE ISOLATION FROM BLACK PEPPER

In a 100 mL round-bottom flask, add at least five boiling chips, 30 mL of dichloromethane, and 15 g of crushed black pepper. heated at reflux for half an hour after attaching a water-jacketed condenser. used a rotary evaporator to concentrate the filtrate after rinsing the pepper solids with up to 15 mL of dichloromethane. After cooling the residue in an ice bath and adding 5–10 mL of cold diethyl ether to the flask, the residue was triturated until the ether was well mixed in to eliminate any remaining dichloromethane. At this stage, precipitation might start. used the rotary evaporator to remove the ether. Repeat the chilling, trituration, and evaporation steps if the leftover residue still seems greasy. Dissolve as much of the residue as you can in 10–15 milliliters of 95% ethanol once it seems to have solidified. The ethanolic pepper extract was added to 10 mL of a 10% potassium hydroxide in 95% ethanol solution that was in a 125 mL Erlenmeyer flask. Use a tiny quantity of 95% ethanol to wash any solids that haven't dissolved into the KOH flask. Using a Pasteur pipette, gradually add water to the heated solution (tricking the water down the flask's sides). The mixture should become cloudy and a yellow precipitate should begin to form. Until the volume reaches 100 mL, keep adding water progressively. After labeling the flask and covering it with parafilm, the mixture was let to stand for a full day. Using the tiny Buchner funnel, collect the solid by suction filtration. Then, wash the solid with two 5 mL portions of water. After being dried, the final

In a small evaporating dish, dissolve 1.12 g of piperine (0.004 mol) and 0.4305 ml (0.004 mol) of o-toluidine with ethanol. The mixture is then boiled for 20 minutes on a boiling water bath. Using a glass rod, stir the mixture often until water globules started to form on the oil's surface. The oil crystallizes quickly after the basin has been cooled in water and well stirred. moved the solid to a conical flask with a capacity of 50 ml..^[14]

SPECTRAL DATA OF THE NEWLY SYNTHESIS COMPOUNDS

The spectrum information gathered from IR, UV, NMR, and mass was used to establish the structures of every freshly synthesized chemical. A single area on TLC plates was used to track the compounds' purity. Ethanol was the solvent utilized.

Compound code: PIP- 4

Fig 3: Structure of PIP-4

UV SPECTRUM

Solvent used: Ethanol

Max. wavelength: 246nm

Fig 4: UV Spectrum of PIP-4

FOURIER TRANSFORM INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (FTIR)

Fig 5: FTIR Spectrum of PIP-4

Table 3: IR spectral value of compound PIP 4

S.NO	Type of vibrations	Frequency (cm-1)
1	Sp ² CH Stretch	2924
2	Sp ³ CH Stretch	2854
3	C=N Stretch	1627
4	C=C Aromatic stretch	1581

Spectral data of the newly synthesized compounds

The spectrum information gathered from IR, UV, NMR, and mass was used to establish the structures of every newly synthesized chemical. A single area on TLC plates was used to track the compounds' purity. Ethanol was the solvent utilized.

Compound code : PIP 5

Fig 6: Structure of PIP-5

UV SPECTRUM

Solvent used : Ethanol

Max. wavelength : 254nm

Fig 7: UV Spectrum of PIP-5

FOURIER TRANSFORM INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (FTIR)

Fig 8: FTIR Spectrum of PIP-5

Table 4: IR spectral value of compound PIP 5

S.NO	Type of vibrations	Frequency (cm-1)
1.	Sp ² CH Stretch	2924
2.	Sp ³ CH Stretch	2854
3.	C=N Stretch	1627
4.	C=C Aromatic stretch	1581

Spectral data of the newly synthesized compounds

The spectrum information gathered from IR, UV, NMR, and mass was used to establish the structures of every newly synthesized chemical. A single area on TLC plates was used to track the compounds' purity. Ethanol was the solvent utilized.

Compound code : PIP 26

Fig 9: UV Spectrum of PIP-5

UV SPECTRUM

Solvent used : Ethanol

Max. wavelength : 254nm

Fig 10: UV Spectrum of PIP-5

FOURIER TRANSFORM INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (FTIR)

Figure 11: FTIR Spectrum of PIP-5

Table 5: IR spectral value of compound PIP 26

S.NO	Type of vibrations	Frequency (cm-1)
1	Sp CH Stretch	2924
2	Sp ³ CH Stretch	2854
3	C=N Stretch	1627
4	C=C Aromatic stretch	1581

In Vitro Enzyme Inhibitory Assay

Enzyme Inhibitory Assay in Vitro

Acetylcholinesterase inhibitory test in vitro

Ellman's approach served as the basis for the assay used to evaluate the enzyme inhibition. The reaction mixture's final volume (4.0 ml) is made up of 1.3 ml of Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0; 50 mM) treated with 0.4 ml of various concentrations (0.2 to 3.2 µg/ml) of the chosen piperine derivatives (PIP-4, 5, and 26). Additionally, 0.1 ml of AChE (0.28 U/ml) was added to the mixture. 0.3 ml of acetylthiocholine iodide (0.023 mg/ml) and 1.9 ml of 5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid) DTNB (3 mM) solution were added to this combination after it had been incubated for 15 minutes. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 405 nm after the final reaction mixture (4 ml) was further incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature. The medication was swapped out for an appropriate solvent to provide the control. To counteract the influence of the test drug's color, the blank was made by substituting the solvent (water) for all of the reagents. Every assay determination was carried out in triplicate, and the standard error of the mean was used to express the

findings. The following formula was used to get the % inhibition:

$$\% \text{ Acetylcholinesterase inhibition} = \frac{(A_0 - A_1)}{A_0} \times 100$$

A₀ Absorbance of the control

A₁ Absorbance of the standard/compounds.^[15]

Butyrylcholinesterase inhibitory test in vitro

Ellman's approach served as the basis for the assay used to evaluate the enzyme inhibition. The final volume (4.0 ml) of the reaction mixture is made up of 0.1 ml of BuChE (0.377 U/ml) and 1.3 ml of Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0; 50 mM) treated with 0.4 ml of various concentrations (0.2 to 3.2 µg/ml) of the chosen piperine derivatives (PIP -4,5&26). 0.3 ml of butyrylthiocholine iodide (15 mM) and 1.9 ml of 5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid) DTNB (3 mM) solution were added to this combination after it had been incubated for 15 minutes. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 405 nm after the final reaction mixture (4 mL) was further incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature. The medication was swapped out for an appropriate solvent to provide the control. To counteract the influence of the test

drug's color, the blank was made by substituting the solvent (water) for all of the reagents. Every assay determination would be carried out in triplicate, and the standard error of the mean was used to express the results. The following formula was used to get the % inhibition:

$$\% \text{ Butyrylcholinesterase inhibition} = (A0 - A1) / A0 \times 100$$

A0 Absorbance of the control

A1 Absorbance of the standard/compounds.^[15]

RESULTS

IN SILICO STUDIES

Evaluation of drug likeness properties of the PIP compounds

Table 8: List of semisynthetic derivatives of piperine selected for in silico study in Scheme

Sl. No.	Compound code	R	Sl. No.	Compound code	R
1.	PIP 1	-C6H5	14.	PIP14	-C6H2(OH)3
2.	PIP 2	-C6H4(COOH)	15.	PIP15	-C6H3(NO2)(Cl)
3.	PIP 3	-C6H4(OH)	16.	PIP16	-C6H3(NO2)(Br)
4.	PIP 4	-C6H4(Cl)	17.	PIP17	-C6H3(NO2)(F)
5.	PIP 5	-C6H4(F)	18.	PIP18	-C6H3(OH)(Cl)
6.	PIP 6	-C6H3(F)2	19.	PIP19	-C6H3(OH)(Br)
7.	PIP 7	-C6H4(Br)	20.	PIP 20	-C6H3(OH)(F)
8.	PIP 8	-C6H4(CH3)	21.	PIP 21	-C6H2(Br)(Cl)2
9.	PIP 9	-C6H4(OCH3)	22.	PIP 22	-C6H2(F)(Cl)2
10.	PIP 10	-C6H3(Cl)2	23.	PIP 23	-C6H3(NO2)2
11.	PIP 11	-C6H3(Br)2	24.	PIP 24	-C6H3(Cl)(Br)
12.	PIP 12	-C6H4(NO2)	25.	PIP 25	-C6H3(Cl)(F)
13.	PIP 13	-C6H2(OH)3	26.	PIP 26	-C6H4(CH3)

Molinspiration:

Table 9: Calculation of molecular properties of PIP 1 TO PIP 26 and standard using the Molinspiration online tool

S.No	Compound Code	Log P	Molecular Weight	noN	nOHNH	Violation
1	PIP1	6.08	374.48	4	0	1
2	PIP2	5.54	404.47	6	1	1
3	PIP3	5.15	376.46	5	1	1
4	PIP4	6.31	394.9	4	0	1
5	PIP5	5.79	378.45	4	0	1
6	PIP6	6.44	439.35	4	0	1

7	PIP7	6.08	374.48	4	0	1
8	PIP8	5.69	390.48	5	0	1
9	PIP9	6.92	429.35	4	0	1
10	PIP10	5.89	396.44	4	0	1
11	PIP11	7.18	518.25	4	0	2
12	PIP12	5.59	405.45	7	0	1
13	PIP13	4.37	408.45	7	3	0
14	PIP14	4.57	408.45	7	3	0
15	PIP15	6.2	439.9	7	0	1
16	PIP16	6.33	484.35	7	0	1
17	PIP17	5.52	425.46	7	1	1
18	PIP18	5.76	410.9	5	1	1
19	PIP19	5.89	455.35	5	1	1
20	PIP20	5.24	394.45	5	1	1
21	PIP21	7.65	508.24	4	0	2
22	PIP22	7.01	447.34	4	0	1
23	PIP23	5.48	450.45	10	0	1
24	PIP24	7.05	473.8	4	0	1
25	PIP25	6.4	412.89	4	0	1
26	PIP26	6.03	374.48	4	0	1

ADMET studies

Table 10: Calculated ADMET properties of PIP compounds using the Pre-ADMET online tool

S.NO	HIA	BBB	CaCO2	Buffer solubility	MDCK	Plasma protein binding
1	99.173587	0.925167	57.2455	46.4473	0.429947	91.695321
2	98.26844	0.0459009	30.9481	346.689	0.0672998	90.754497
3	96.258348	1.98541	53.2256	55.6317	0.137684	93.463682
4	99.285128	2.38081	57.1815	27.6577	0.270315	95.322625
5	99.175702	1.24647	56.985	87.9312	0.172115	95.370442
6	99.330086	2.65283	57.0795	12.7471	0.030467	98.5528
7	99.200316	1.84223	57.4527	32.9929	0.337713	91.842411
8	97.752979	0.277948	56.4917	43.731	0.145559	91.655392
9	98.339979	4.83517	57.2537	9.75139	0.231562	96.182992
10	99.177813	1.58695	56.572	99.0953	0.355373	94.387283
11	99.310075	5.65515	57.3071	2.01993	0.0196114	99.426156
12	98.941157	0.0556175	35.4073	9.0962	0.0627637	90.182165
13	92.018512	1.14277	14.617	1279.83	0.0704971	93.065483
14	92.021063	1.2539	16.3771	74.8862	0.114843	92.637487
15	98.202959	0.0615486	35.6797	3.20038	0.0554881	100
16	97.777579	0.0624536	36.8783	1.45975	0.0236094	100
17	96.712402	0.164022	31.1867	0.276603	0.0610088	90.436385
18	96.682707	3.97454	50.1606	19.6913	0.104507	94.206414
19	96.919188	4.27459	48.8256	9.03973	0.023023	94.761455
20	96.265893	2.49288	52.8864	62.7099	0.213828	92.983324
21	99.288107	8.47015	57.3856	1.01653	0.0187224	98.415331
22	99.340335	5.61327	57.166	7.16512	1.54488	97.331365
23	95.2317	0.476779	14.6538	1.04975	0.0510306	95.973073
24	99.339901	5.2347	57.2424	4.45781	0.0213856	99.440496
25	99.286535	2.9319	57.3233	31.1103	0.146035	95.696652
26	99.200316	1.86439	57.3604	18.4855	0.316585	91.666796

DOCKING STUDIES:

Table 11: Binding energies of PIP1 to PIP26 with AChE(4ey7)

S.No	Binding energy	Intermolecular energy	Inhibition constant
1	-11.59	-13.08	3.19
2	-9.26	-11.35	163.7
3	-2.8	-4.59	8.86
4	-0.72	-2.21	298.23
5	-4.66	-6.15	382.6
6	-2.06	-3.55	30.99mM
7	-4.34	-5.83	656.02μM
8	1.3	-0.49	Unavailable
9	-3.58	-5.07	2.36nM
10	-4.6	-6.09	425.07UM
11	-2.18	-3.67	25.44mM
12	3.52	1.72	Unavailable
13	-1.84	-4.23	44.75mM
14	-4.03	-6.41	1.12mM
15	1.93	0.14	Unavailable
16	6.66	4.87	Unavailable
17	-4.78	-6.87	313.45μM
18	-4.97	-6.76	228.47μM
19	-4.4	-6.19	598.85μM
20	-2.92	-4.71	7.23mM
21	-2.09	-3.58	29.56mM
22	-4.34	-5.83	658.09μM
23	-4.75	-6.83	331.79UM
24	-1.39	-2.88	95.58mM
25	-4.94	-6.43	238.07μM
26	-4.95	-6.44	235.1uM

Table 12: Binding energies of PIP1 to PIP26 with BuChE(4BDS)

S.No	Binding energy	Intermolecular energy	Inhibition constant
1	-7.83	-9.32	1.83μM
2	-1.49	-3.58	81.18mM
3	-8.92	-10.71	290.09nM
4	-8.72	-10.21	406.68nM
5	-7.74	-9.23	2.12μM
6	-2.3	-3.79	20.56mM
7	-3.97	-5.46	1.24mM
8	-3.44	-5.23	3.02mM
9	-2.4	-3.89	17.32mM
10	-4.4	-5.89	597.73μM
11	-1.3	-2.79	111.81mM
12	-3.3	-5.09	3.78mM
13	-3.88	-6.27	1.43mM
14	-3.25	-5.64	4.14mM
15	-1.55	-3.34	73.13mM
16	-1.76	-3.55	51.4mM
17	-9.59	-11.68	93.03nM
18	-4.48	-6.27	519.46μM
19	-4.72	-6.51	344.85 μM

20	-3.92	-5.71	1.33mM
21	-2.44	-3.93	16.23mM
22	-1.97	-3.47	35.69mM
23	2.77	0.68	UNAVAILABLE
24	-2.01	-3.5	33.67mM
25	-5.08	-6.57	189.91UM
26	-6.21	-7.7	27.93UM

Fig.12 PIP4 BINDING WITH AChE (4EY7.PDB)
BINDING ENERGY : -0.72kcal/mol

Fig.13 PIP5 BINDING WITH AChE (4EY7.PD)
BINDING ENERGY : -4.66kcal/mol

Fig.14 PIP4 BINDING WITH BuChE (4BDS.PDB)
BINDING ENERGY : -8.72kcal/mol

Fig.15. PIP5 BINDING WITH BuChE (4BDS.PDB)
BINDING ENERGY : -7.66kcal/mol

Fig.16 PIP26 BINDING WITH AChE (4EY7.PDB) Fig.17 PIP26 BINDING WITH BuChE (4EY7.PDB)
BINDING ENERGY : -4.95kcal/mol BINDING ENERGY : -6.21kcal/mol

IN VITRO CHOLINESTERASE INHIBITORY STUDY:

Table 13 AChE inhibitory activity of different concentrations of Piperine derivatives and standard

Compound Code	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)							IC ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
	10	20	40	80	160	320	640	
PIP4	39.89± 0.01	43.91± 0.09	47.58± 0.04	52.01± 0.05	56.24± 0.05	59.54± 0.04	62.42± 0.06	70±0.54
PIP5	40.45± 0.11	44.07± 0.14	48.49± 0.05	53±0.0 4	56.57± 0.08	60.65± 0.05	62.69± 0.07	56±0.45
PIP26	40.99± 0.11	44.52± 0.16	48.11± 0.03	52.8±0. 02	56.96± 0.11	60.79± 0.04	62.59± 0.05	58±0.05
Rivastigmine	47.26± 0.27	49.54± 0.85	53.74± 0.63	57.04± 0.68	59.49± 0.38	62.45± 0.55	64.11± 1.36	25±0.34

IN VITRO BUTYRYLCHOLINESTERASE INHIBITORY STUDY:

Table 14: BUChe inhibitory activity of different concentrations of Piperine derivatives and standard

Compound Code	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)							IC ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
	10	20	40	80	160	320	640	
PIP4	40.9± 0.04	43.51± 0.03	47.60± 0.03	50.17± 0.07	53.98± 0.07	56.84± 0.08	60.94± 0.04	76±0.55
PIP5	41.20± 0.02	46.76± 0.01	50.87± 0.04	55.80± 0.04	58.67± 0.03	59.64± 0.05	61.86± 0.01	30±0.32
PIP26	39.96± 0.03	45.69± 0.03	48.65± 0.03	54.56± 0.04	57.27± 0.01	60.12± 0.05	61.98± 0.03	54±0.72
Rivastigmine	35.41± 0.28	38.24± 0.48	43.05± 1.25	52.98± 0.44	55.29± 0.20	57.96± 0.51	64.11± 1.36	60±0.36

All the determinations were carried out in triplicate, and the values are expressed as the mean \pm SEM

DISCUSSION

A neurodegenerative condition, Alzheimer's disease gradually impairs behavioral and cognitive abilities such as memory, comprehension, language, attention, thinking, and judgment. In the US, it ranks as the sixth

most common cause of death. The most prevalent type of dementia, Alzheimer's disease (AD), affects millions of individuals globally. Brain vascular dysfunction, which leads to reduced brain perfusion, is one of the main causes of AD pathogenesis. Furthermore, vascular disruption and reduced cognitive function result from the decreased clearance of excess neurotoxic amyloid beta (AB) brought on by the breakdown of the blood-brain barrier's (BBB) protective role. Vascular risk factors and the prevalence of AD have a complicated and poorly understood relationship. We demonstrate the vascular risk factors, their impact on BBB function, and their role in the development of AD in this review. We also go over the underlying causes of cerebral hypoperfusion and/or impaired neurovascular function in AD. Many medicinal plants with strong effects on the central nervous system and antioxidant activity have drawn a lot of interest lately as dietary supplements to enhance cognitive function in the face of illnesses that impair cognitive function, such as Alzheimer's disease. Based on this knowledge, research has been done on the impact of piperine, the primary active alkaloid found in *Piper nigrum* fruit, on Alzheimer's disease neurodegeneration and memory function. The reduction in lipid peroxidation and the acetylcholinesterase enzyme may be somewhat linked to the potential underlying causes. Additionally, piperine showed neurotrophic benefits in the hippocampal region. Alzheimer's disease is a neurological disorder that results in dementia and cognitive impairment. The mutant Amyloid precursor protein (APP) fragments that self-aggregate are the cause of the pathogenic lesions and neuronal damage in the brain. The method for lowering the AB burden in Alzheimer's disease treatment is regulated APP processing through secretase inhibition. In the search for a successful anti-AD treatment, bioinformatics, cheminformatics, and ADME Tox techniques can be highly beneficial. They enable the discovery of new medications, improve the drugs' capacity to target molecular targets, and offer a better comprehension of the pathogenic mechanisms underlying ME. In medical chemistry, the quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) is a highly helpful method for examining how synthetic or natural molecules interact with their targets, such as enzymes or membrane receptors. This approach is particularly helpful when it's necessary to estimate the biological activities of

"uncharacterized" natural chemicals quickly. According to QSAR methodologies, a compound's chemical structure dictates its biological activity, and a change in a compound's chemical structure alters its biological activity. The creation of QSAR models varies by program. For example, the biological activity of chemicals in 2D QSAR is computed as follows: $(\log 1/\text{experimental properties of substances}) = \text{const} + (C_1 \cdot d_1) + (C_2 \cdot d_2) + (C_3 \cdot d_3) + \dots$, and biological activity.

Amyloid-cascade and hyperphosphorylated tau-cascade hypotheses, which are closely associated with macromolecules known as enzymes like β - & γ -secretases, cholinesterase, transglutaminases, glycogen synthase kinase (GSK-3), cyclin-dependent kinase (cdk-5), and microtubule affinity-regulating kinase (MARK), are the main focus of Alzheimer's disease, a degenerative disease of the brain cells. Cognitive difficulties, memory impairment, synapse malfunction and loss, and finally neuronal death are the causes of the catalytic activity of the aforementioned enzymes. When reduced to their normal activities and levels in the brain, other enzymes, such as secretases, protein kinase C, phosphatases, etc., that are metabolized to neurotransmitters, such as catechol-O-methyltransferase (COMT) and monoamine oxidase (MAO), also cause these dysfunctional events.

Out of the 26 chemicals utilized in the study, three piperine derivatives—PIP-4, PIP-5, and PIP-26—were chosen based on the *in silico* results. The chosen piperine derivatives were examined for their ability to inhibit different enzymes, including butyrylcholinesterase and acetylcholinesterase, *in vitro*. The inhibitory experiment demonstrated that each of the chosen piperine derivatives have the ability to inhibit enzymes. In particular, PIP-5 has greater potential than rivastigmine and the other piperine derivatives and conventional medications.

CONCLUSION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is typically treated with acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors; however, these medications have many drawbacks, including dose limiting and suboptimal long-term therapeutic outcomes. However, compared to particular AChE inhibitors, butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) inhibitors

or combined acetyl and butyryl cholinesterase inhibitors have fewer adverse effects and better curative results on AD, according to recent studies. Dual target cholinesterase inhibitors have emerged as a new area of interest in anti-AD medication research. Therefore, when compared to the common medication rivastigmine, molecular docking studies utilizing AutoDock 4.2 for manufactured piperine derivatives (PIP 4, PIP 5, and PIP 26) using AChE and BuChE enzymes produced intriguing results. Its anti-Alzheimer activity was discovered by virtual screening tests and a subsequent in vitro assessment using the AChE and BuChE inhibition assay. Acetylcholine levels are raised via enzyme inhibition tests employing AChE and BuChE, which helps AD patients' cognitive performance. These artificially produced piperine derivatives may also serve as building blocks or precursors for the creation of more potent medication molecules that might prevent or halt the progression of Alzheimer's disease. Before these compounds can be evaluated in human volunteers, more in vitro research using appropriate cell lines, in vivo, and molecular level works are needed to confirm the anti-Alzheimer's activity and to support the findings of PIP 4, PIP 5, and PIP 26.

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